

USING THE PROJECT METHOD IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CREATIVE SKILLS

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the use of the project method in these processes, its importance, and the resulting situations, based on the collected sources, as a result of the study of the issues of development of creative abilities of schoolchildren.*

Keywords: *creativity, student, school, project method, formation of creative approach, creative ability, improvement of professional training.*

One of the leading directions of the reform of general education is the humanitarian paradigm, which provides for the creation of conditions for the manifestation of individuality, the identification and optimal development of a person's creative potential. It should also be noted that the priority task of general education is to form not only the intellect of students, but also the spiritual and emotional sphere, creative approach to work, which is a prerequisite for the effectiveness of future professional activities and social adjustment of school graduates.

In today's modern conditions, it is necessary to develop new approaches and solutions to determine the right strategy for the formation of creative abilities of a person. For this, it is appropriate to critically analyze the existing and possible options of socio-economic and political behavior, to forecast the development of the field of human activity with various behaviors and various management decisions based on relevant scientific developments and recommendations.

Therefore, one of the priorities of the modern general education school is to form a highly cultured, wide and deep, constantly renewing and developing creative, bold and free-thinking person, to recognize the interest in creativity as a result of effective use of various methods must.

Creativity is an important aspect of learning. Thanks to creativity, the student has a positive attitude towards learning and his learning becomes more interesting. Creativity causes the learner to activate passive information by turning it into a product. Thanks to creativity acquired from a young age, people can easily solve problems in their daily lives and become more effective in adulthood. This is one of the main goals of education: to equip students for their future lives and to raise them to be productive citizens. Therefore, at the same time, attention is being paid to the issue of developing the creative abilities of the students of the republic, the actively used forms and tools in this regard, and their importance.

Currently, in every educational process at school, the teacher performs a new task that aims to prepare students to become successful people in life and provides them with the skills of the 21st century. The topic of developing students' creative abilities and the methods and tools used in this is no exception.

It is expected to develop students' creative abilities, and the methods and tools used in this will also develop students' intellectual abilities to adapt to different conditions, respect society, and treat ideas with tolerance. It is known that the important skills of the 21st century include special skills that should be strengthened in educational activities, namely critical thinking and

creative skills, problem solving, metabolizing, communication skills, cooperation, innovation, are higher-order thinking skills such as creativity and information literacy.

One of the main tasks of pedagogy is to create conditions that ensure the comprehensive development of creative activity of all students. In addition, it is necessary to identify students who show deep interest, desire and ability in certain fields, and to create all opportunities for their further development. For this, it is important to create conditions for the development of creative activity of school-aged students. At the same time, it increases the place and level of importance of forms, methods and tools used in the development of students' creative abilities. In this regard, the teacher's efforts are also considered very important. Because the preparation of teachers for innovative activities related to the development of creative activity, the creation of cooperative activities in the relationship between teachers and students, the use of innovative technologies, modern methods, the most advanced effective forms and tools for the development of creative activity, practical work is the most effective in developing creative abilities.

Traditional and modern forms, methods and tools used in the development of students' creative abilities show a unique feature when compared with learning methods. This is due to the fact that in the process of teaching, the task is not to discover a new scientific truth, but to creatively assimilate the acquired knowledge. During training, there are much "easier" conditions for acquiring new knowledge, which almost exclude the trial-and-error characteristic of common knowledge. Therefore, it is useful to adapt the forms, methods and tools used for the development of students' creative abilities to the conditions of the educational process, which are combined with cognitive operations. And they directly depend on the age of students. This is where the special features of the forms, methods and tools used in the development of students' creative abilities and their importance in the practical process are revealed.

As one of the methods that includes the same features, the project method can be taken as an example. During the trial period of the research, the same method was used in depth. With this, the primary goal was to develop students' creative abilities.

Socio-cultural and socio-economic changes in the modern Uzbek society demanded a qualitative study of the problems of developing creative abilities in the professional training of future specialists at all levels of education. In the modern conditions of the reform of the continuous professional education system, with its democratization and humanization, students in a number of directions such as "Interior design", "Costume design", "Industrial design" are among the most demanding directions of today's era. the phenomenon of improving professional training and training of various profiles in other educational institutions is of particular importance. It is the changes that are taking place in the life of society that require the development of qualitatively new methods and methods of education, pedagogical technologies, the purpose of which is to develop the individual development of a person, creativity, the ability to form and solve universal abilities, and to solve problems of a professional nature. takes place in the same category.

As a result of detailed reading of encyclopedic dictionaries, it was witnessed that "project" (from Latin) is interpreted as a set of documents (calculations, drawings) for the creation of a structure or product. This means the initial text of practical work: an idea, a plan. Having studied the genesis of the project method, it was found necessary to rely on the following understanding of this term:

A project is a time-limited purposeful change of a particular system with quality requirements, results, possible scope of expenditure and a specific organization. As a rule, design

begins with the development of a future model (technology, content, product, etc.) as an integral part of the conceptual description. The project is not separated from the surrounding conditions and their development. However, according to experts, it is recommended not to take into account the influence of all factors that can affect the activity of innovative development (to abstract from their influence) when developing the model as an integral part of the project at this stage.

The project method (Greek - "research") is emphasized as an educational system in which students acquire knowledge in the process of planning projects and performing progressively more complex practical tasks. If we refer to the main features of the project method, then the relevance of the project to the future; directing the project to the desired state; presentation of the project as a system of means of achievement; determining the beginning and end of project work; clearly defined performance criteria; it is necessary to take into account that the changed socio-economic conditions can change the moral and pedagogical ideals, principles and foundations of school life. Each social upheaval carries with it the demands of a new school, its approach to the changed forms of life.

As a result of working with this method among the 7th grade students of the selected object during the research, the goal is to develop their creative abilities. Based on this, the age characteristics of the students are not left out of consideration. That is, of course, practical processes were organized in accordance with their age characteristics.

It can be said that the problem was seriously discussed in the practical processes of the research. Which of the targeted actions that make up the content of school life can be considered the most effective, should it be prioritized, pedagogically encouraged and promoted? It was planned to solve this question very simply, relying on simple, everyday observational data and the latest conclusions of experimental psychological research. He makes the following proposition that the unquestionable measure of value is the degree of interest of the learner, the degree of sincere enthusiasm for the object at hand, the last consideration on which, in his opinion, any scientific system of education must be based. Found a very serious confirmation by the science of psychology.

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